

CAUSES OF VIOLATIONS IN READING AND WRITING AS WELL AS WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM

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ABSTRACT

Disorders in Reading and writing lead to difficulties in the educational process and in everyday life of children. These disorders are represented by conditions such as dyslexia and dysgraphia. In this article we will talk about the causes of the origin of disorders in reading and writing, their types and ways of elimination.

ПРИЧИНЫ НАРУШЕНИЙ ЧТЕНИЯ И ПИСЬМА И ПУТИ ИХ УСТРАНЕНИЯ

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ABSTRACT

Нарушения в чтении и письме приводят к трудностям в учебном процессе и в повседневной жизни детей. Эти нарушения представлены такими состояниями, как дислексия и дисграфия. В этой статье мы поговорим о причинах возникновения нарушений в чтении и письме, их видах и способах устранения.

Dyslexia is a disorder in the development of reading skills that involves difficulties in identifying, pronouncing, and understanding words.

Signs: confusion of letters, incorrect reading of words, difficulties in understanding the read text.

Dysgraphia is a disorder in the development of writing skills that involves difficulties in writing letters and words correctly.

Signs: misspelling letters, juxtaposing words, non-compliance with grammatical rules.

Reasons for the origin of disorders in reading and writing.

Genetic Factors:

Heredity: studies show that there are genetic factors for disorders in reading and writing. If parents have dyslexia or dysgraphia, the child will also be more likely to experience these disorders.

Neurological Factors:

Brain activity: there are peculiarities in brain activity that are associated with dyslexia and dysgraphia. This affects the ability of children to learn and use the language.

Perception and cognitive abilities: developmental disorders of perception and cognitive abilities necessary for reading and writing skills. Cognitive impairment does not remain without showing its negative effects on the child's cognitive processes as well as the development of Ali.

Environmental factors:

Education system: low educational conditions and quality of children. This has an effect, especially in the process of learning to read and write.

Social and family factors: Children's home conditions, active participation of parents in the process of education and upbringing.

Psychological Factors:

Mental health: mental health and emotional state of children. Depression, anxiety, and other psychological problems can lead to reading and writing disorders. This is mainly due to the unhealthy atmosphere in the family, the fact that the relationship with the child is not good

Ways to eliminate reading and writing disorders

Early diagnosis and intervention:

Diagnostics: early detection of dyslexia and dysgraphia is important. These disorders can be detected through special tests and diagnostic methods.

Intervention: it is possible to develop children's reading and writing skills through primary education and speech therapy at an early stage.

Special education methods:

Individual approach: the development of individual educational programs in accordance with the needs of each child.

Multisensory methods: the development of children's reading and writing skills through educational methods that attract many emotions.

Logopedic and psychological support:

Logopedic training: training aimed at the development of articulation, phonetic and phonemic abilities.

Psychological assistance: psychological assistance aimed at improving the emotional and psychological state. This will help increase children's interest in reading and writing.

Technological tools:

Computer programs and applications: special computer programs and mobile applications that help eliminate problems with dyslexia and dysgraphia.

Interactive educational tools: development of children's reading and writing skills using interactive whiteboards and other technological tools.

Support from parents and educators:

Parents: it is important for parents to understand and support their children's difficulties in reading and writing.

Educators: educators must take into account the individual needs of children using special educational methods.

The reasons for the origin of disorders in reading and writing depend on various factors, and a multidirectional approach is necessary to eliminate them. Through early diagnosis and interventionism, special education methods, logopedic and psychological support, technological tools and the support of parents and educators, children's difficulties in reading and writing can be effectively overcome.

Such defects are often overlooked. Because neither the school pedagogue nor the parent will carry out the correction of this defect in the child with the idea that it will disappear temporarily, after time has passed. Over the years, the effect of a defect in a child will increase, his mental development, ability to think will develop sluggishly from the norm of imagination and thinking, attention. The consequence of this is a state of lagging behind peers in terms of Child Development Indicators.

To prevent such situations, it is recommended to establish individual control with each child, monitor him, and take measures to timely eliminate the defects and disorders encountered.

We have provided information about the many causes of origin of the above reading and writing disorders, as well as measures to eliminate them. The opportunity to provide the most first aid and the greatest effectiveness in eliminating any defect is properly organized correctional training conducted with a specialist in a timely manner, as well as selected effective methods suitable for the defect. For this reason, we will mention that it is necessary that every single parent is attentive to the development of their child and that it creates a healthy environment for its development.

In the fertilizer forms of violations in reading and writing, it is necessary to work not only with a defectologist-speech therapist, but also with a medical worker and a psychologist. Because in this there may be organic injuries to the child's brain or psychological causes that strongly affect him. Each Specialist will work with the child in a different direction and achieve the desired result.

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